

ETHNO-PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATING FUTURE TEACHERS WITH A SENSE OF NATIONAL PRIDE

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Abstract. This article discusses the ethno-pedagogical features of educating future teachers based on a sense of national pride. Also, in the article, some thoughts are expressed about the importance of ethno-pedagogical values in instilling in students today a sense of love for the homeland, its present, past and future.

Keywords. Value, education, national pride, promotion, patriotism, idea, aspiration, relationship.

Абстрактный. В данной статье рассматриваются этнопедагогические особенности воспитания будущих учителей на основе чувства национальной гордости. Также в статье высказываются некоторые мысли о значении этнопедагогических ценностей в воспитании у школьников сегодня чувства любви к Родине, ее настоящему, прошлому и будущему.

Ключевые слова. Ценность, воспитание, национальная гордость, пропаганда, патриотизм, идея, стремление, отношения.

INTRODUCTION.

The fact that a particular nation has a unique status and place in the world community does not depend on its large or small number. On the contrary, the ability to manifest national characteristics, the deep understanding of the rights of the representatives of the nation, not to be materially and morally dependent on other nations, and to exist independently determines its status in the international arena.

Being able to boldly express one's views on international relations, fight for the honor and reputation of the nation, and strive to prevent the formation of negative attitudes towards oneself in other nations will further increase the prestige of the nation.

In determining the position of the nation in the international arena, it is also important to establish the progressive ideas that take priority in the society and the life of the society based on them. For this reason, in the society of our country, special attention is being paid to the formation of historical memory, historical consciousness, love for the homeland and pride in its history, and the education of the young generation in the spirit of this idea.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

At the meeting of the video selector chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard, "If the body of society's life is the economy, its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values", [1] it is not for nothing that they emphasized.

As the President noted, in building a new Uzbekistan, we rely on the strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values for the development of society. It is no exaggeration to say that the slogan "New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold" embodies the practical importance of today's reforms. At the same time, it is necessary to improve the quality of future pedagogues who share education, spirituality and culture with students in the school education system, to educate them in the spirit of love for the motherland, to have a deep understanding of its history, in a word, to develop the national culture. The need to arm with urur and historical memory is becoming more urgent than ever. After all, personal education, human maturity is an important factor that determines the development of the country. Today, the factors directly and indirectly affecting the formation of personality should be taken into account. Such factors include not only material, ideological, and psychological conditions, but also the environment in which the personality was formed. This process is also influenced by inter-ethnic relations and national politics in different countries. This has a great impact on the formation of personal qualities. If we take into account that such qualities include concepts such as national self-awareness, pride, pride, it can be concluded that the moral formation of a person is closely related to universal values.[2.44]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

It is known that the issues of national pride, historical memory, learning of one's own history are combined with the science of Sufism in the Eastern pedagogy, which has been an important source in the formation of the spirituality of our people for thousands of years. Sharifs, as well as the great thinkers Muhammad Ismail al-Bukhari, Muhammad Isa al-Tirmizi, Mahmoud Kashgari, Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, Amir Temur, Alisher Nawai, expressed in the form of rare ideas in the scientific heritage .

We can see the confirmation of these thoughts from Abu Rayhan Beruni's comments on the teacher's work. Beruni believed that choosing a teacher to teach young people is the first and main task of parents. For this, the teacher needs to be polite, honest, well-versed in his subject and the rules of teaching, well-aware of his history, clean, and exemplary in walking and standing. If, - says Beruni, - the educator himself is not an example, if he does not follow what he says, then his demands and upbringing are ineffective. [3.12]

In the works of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, who are among the founders of the pedagogy of the new era, education and the role and services of the teacher in this process are interpreted in their own way based on the socio-political life of the time. In particular, Abdulla Avloni focuses on the work of a teacher and places the responsibility of the child's intellectual development on the school, not on the family, but on the teachers: "Thought education is the most necessary, sacred duty that has been honored for many times, relied on the attention of teachers, and entrusted to the conscience of teachers. Thought makes a person noble, enthusiastic. This education needs the help of teachers, because the strength, ornamentation, and breadth of thought depends on the teacher's education." [4.16]

As can be seen above, the development of the country and the education of children depend on teachers. That is why it is imperative to educate today's future teachers to be mature and perfect in all aspects. It is necessary to determine not only their professional knowledge, but also their national and historical knowledge. Enriching their professional skills with national pride and historical consciousness will be the bold steps taken by future teachers towards perfection.

The problem of forming the professional competence of future teachers based on a sense of national pride is of a social nature. Therefore, the formation of a sense of national pride in future teachers encourages them to selflessly work for the development of the country, prosperity and well-being of the people. Also, the formation of the skills to fight for the stability of peace and security in the society in which they live, to contribute to the settlement of mutual harmony between people of different nationalities and ethnicities, and to be a representative of the nation. ensures that they realize their value.

Studying history leads to the rise of national pride in future pedagogues. Studying the cultural heritage of the past is a complex process. It is necessary to inculcate examples of cultural heritage and the noble ideas put forward in them into the minds of the young generation in a continuous, consistent, systematic and purposeful way.[5.58]

Forming the professional competence of future teachers based on a sense of national pride is a process of pedagogical activity that requires a long-term, systematic and consistent approach. This process is considered an important component of the overall process of realizing the social goal of educating a well-rounded person and qualified specialist.

In the way of building a new Uzbekistan, attention is being paid to the creation of an environment that ensures the formation of a person in an all-round mature and well-rounded way, and large-scale actions are being implemented in this way. Regulatory documents aimed at raising the status of the teacher and increasing his place in the life of the society were developed and put into practice.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev said, "Today's rapidly changing world is opening up new and great opportunities for humanity and young people. At the same time, they are exposed to various evil dangers that have not been seen before. Malicious forces are turning the children against their parents and their country, taking their lives. In such a tense and dangerous situation, we parents, teachers-coaches, the public, the neighborhood should increase vigilance and awareness in this matter. We should raise our children ourselves, not leave them in the hands of others. For this, we need to talk more with our youth, listen to their hearts, understand their pain, and give them practical help to solve their problems. In this regard, we need to pay special attention to work with unorganized youth. It is not for nothing that they say that in the implementation of these tasks, we rely on the rich heritage of our ancestors, our national traditions formed over the centuries. Because our rich cultural heritage and traditions formed over the centuries not only shape the human psyche, national pride and national pride, but also serve to educate a person with love for the motherland and concern for its past, present and future. For this, first of all, it is an important and urgent task to educate the future pedagogues who will educate and educate young people growing up in educational institutions in a way that is relevant to the needs of the times, with regard to nationality and history, and to grow their national pride.

In order to determine the formation of a sense of national pride in future teachers, it is necessary to understand the essence of this concept. Therefore, based on the analysis of its coverage in the sources, we will try to create criteria that help to determine the level of formation of the sense of national pride in future teachers.

CONCLUSION

"Development", "education", "formation", "factor", "pedagogical influence", "national pride" in highlighting the nature of activities aimed at forming the professional competence of future teachers based on a sense of national pride, concepts such as "national pride" and "awareness

of national identity" appear as basic concepts. In order to positively solve the research problem, it is necessary to fully understand the content of these concepts.

In many literature, it is noted that the concepts of "formation", "development", "education", and in some sources "socialization" have a single logic. There are also opinions that the concepts of "formation" and "development" are complementary concepts.

Education of a person takes place during the organization of the educational process and determines certain spiritual and moral, voluntary and personal qualities in a person. Education is considered a general and important category of social life. At the same time, it has a number of characteristics as a social phenomenon. For example, passing on experiences accumulated by ancestors to generations, acquiring knowledge created by mankind, ensuring human health and development, forming a worldview, etc. are among these. "Education, first of all, represents the process of personal formation, cultural elements, human and national values, and secondly, it represents the interrelationship of education and culture, and it determines the level of upbringing based on national pride".[6.18] National pride The effectiveness of the education process based on urur is determined by the clear definition of the goal, the results of the activity organized on the basis of the activity, and the indicators reflected in its content.

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